

Current connectivity map of European seas

Deliverable 2.7

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The report represents the most up to date status of the information. Any potential upcoming information may be considered for incorporation in future deliverables to improve the scientific knowledge.

The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 2.7 overview

The present document details the procedures involved in Deliverable 2.7 of MPA Europe, which provides comprehensive oceanographic connectivity estimates for the European coastlines driven by ocean currents and based on biophysical modelling. The information provided will contribute to policy-relevant research focusing on MPA designation, in particular, the capacity of a future MPA network to accommodate species range shifts under ongoing and future climate change.

Background

Marine biogeographic analyses indicate few barriers to dispersal in the ocean, with most being caused by land barriers or extreme isolation (e.g., New Zealand, Antarctica) (Costello et al. 2017). However, the distribution of marine biodiversity may be significantly influenced by oceanographic connectivity, which mediates the movement of planktonic propagules like larvae, spores, and thallus fragments across marine environments. This process is primarily governed by the interaction between ocean currents and the dispersal capabilities of individual species (Gouvêa et al. 2023; Manel et al. 2023) which vary greatly (Assis et al. 2021; Shanks 2009). In addition to almost all marine species having planktonic life-stages that disperse in ocean currents, ~80% of animals can also disperse as juveniles and adults, with only about 20% being sessile or sedentary in the adult stage (Costello and Chaudhary 2017). On the other hand, regardless of a species dispersal, it will only occur where the environment is suitable. Therefore, the longevity of eggs and larvae will also be affected by sea temperature, as warmer temperatures increase metabolic demands and energy reserves depend on parental investment in eggs and feeding ability of larvae. Thus, it is unclear whether ocean currents, environmental suitability, biological traits, or perhaps ecological interactions (e.g., predation), are more important in limiting the distribution of marine species.

While limited dispersal or oceanographic barriers may restrict some species distribution and connectivity, strong currents and high dispersal potential can lead to range expansions and successful colonization of new areas across large water masses (Fraser et al. 2018; Waters et al. 2018; Wernberg et al. 2013).

Graph theoretic approaches, such as the use of centrality indices, provide valuable tools to quantify and understand these complex patterns of connectivity, including the identification of critical connectivity sources and corridors that may warrant prioritization in conservation efforts (Abecasis et al. 2023). They also account for multigenerational “stepping-stone” dispersal. In the context of graph theory, a graph is a data structure that consists of a set of nodes (e.g., coastal areas) and a set of edges that connect pairs of nodes (e.g., connectivity between sites). From a wide-range of centrality metrics, three offer particularly valuable insights in the scope of conservation and management of marine areas:

- (1) *Betweenness centrality* is defined as the sum of the fraction of all-pairs shortest paths that pass through a given node. This metric measures the importance of a node within a graph based on the number of shortest paths that pass through the node. It is useful for identifying areas that may serve as connectivity corridors or pathways (Abecasis et al. 2023; Ospina-Alvarez et al. 2020).
- (2) *Out-strength centrality* is defined as the sum of the weights of its outgoing edges. This centrality metric is particularly useful to quantify the total strength or influence a node exerts on its neighbors by considering the cumulative weight of all connections it initiates. It identifies nodes with the highest potential for propagule dispersal, potentially acting as source areas (Abecasis et al. 2023; Ospina-Alvarez et al. 2020).
- (3) *Harmonic centrality* is defined as the reciprocal of the sum of the shortest path distances from the node to all other nodes. Unlike closeness centrality, harmonic centrality assigns a distance of zero for unreachable nodes, making it applicable to disconnected graphs. This metric evaluates the importance of a node based on its average distance to all other nodes in the network. It indicates an area’s proximity and accessibility to other areas (Opsahl et al. 2010). An area with high harmonic centrality is likely to receive a diverse array of propagules from various sources, making it more resilient to disturbances and better equipped for adaptation. It may be a source and/or a sink area.

Understanding the role that each area plays within the oceanographic connectivity network can inform marine conservation planning and management, as it indicates how areas may contribute to network integrity and facilitate gene flow (Balbar and Metaxas 2019; Ospina-Alvarez et al. 2020).

Methods

Oceanographic connectivity estimates (Assis et al. 2024) were integrated in a graph-theoretic framework to explore centrality indices across a representative range of propagule durations. Surface current connectivity estimates are limited to the European coastal areas because (1) most biodiversity is distributed in the coastal zone and because (2) biophysical models require discrete source and sink areas to effectively simulate and quantify dispersal pathways and settlement probabilities. Simulating dispersal across the entire open ocean would imply that particle settlements in sink areas would be restricted to the vicinity of their source areas.

Propagule duration dataset

We compiled a propagule duration database by expanding on a collection of empirical data for marine species (Assis et al. 2021). This enhanced database contains 45,689 records of propagule duration for 764 marine species (see Assis et al. 2021 and 2024), derived from observations of settlement rates, mortality, and survival of various life stages such as larvae, thallus fragments, and spores. Species were classified into 13 groups: Ascidiacea, Bryozoa, corals, Crustacea, Echinodermata, fish, Hydrozoa, macroalgae, mangroves, Mollusca, Polychaeta, seagrasses, and sponges. Such a database allows linking simulated propagule duration periods and the connectivity patterns of different groups of marine biodiversity.

Oceanographic connectivity estimates and graph theory

A biophysical model was employed to estimate connectivity along global coastlines. The model utilized daily surface data on ocean currents from the Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis GLORYS12V, a Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS, <https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00021>) and comprise two decades of daily direction and intensity of ocean current patterns to advect particles. The biophysical model simulated the dispersal of drifting propagules (larvae, spores, etc.) over a 21-year period (2000-2020), tracking their movement via Lagrangian particles released from the centers of hexagon-shaped coastal sites in European seas, each measuring ~8 km to match GLORYS12V1 data. Each particle was advected by ocean currents for a maximum of 180 days, encompassing the majority of known propagule durations (see Gouvêa et al. 2023, and the 95th percentile of the propagule duration periods in Figure 1 and Figure 2). The position of each particle was calculated hourly through bilinear interpolation, in compliance with the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy condition, until they either reached designated sink sites or got lost to the open ocean (Gouvêa et al. 2023; Legrand et al. 2024). During the simulation period, the realized connections between pair sites were recorded, alongside the corresponding date of particle release and trajectory time.

The GLORYS12V1 reanalysis is a well-validated model incorporating satellite and in-situ data, and has demonstrated accuracy in capturing oceanic processes across various scales. The biophysical model, previously validated against empirical data from diverse marine taxa (Assis et al. 2015; Assis et al. 2022; Buonomo et al. 2016; Cunha et al. 2017; Gouvêa et al. 2023; Klein et al. 2016; Legrand et al. 2024; Lourenço et al. 2017; Tavares et al. 2023), offers valuable insights into coastal connectivity patterns. The simulation was firstly performed globally encompassing 7,670 days, with over 204 million particles released from 26,642 sites, resulting in nearly 195 million pairwise connectivity events (Assis et al. 2024). The resulting data from the global biophysical model

quantifies the probability of connection between any two coastal sites. These data were then extracted for the European coastlines, resulting in a subset of the global simulation with over 26 million particles released from 3,488 sites, that resulted in nearly 25.8 million pairwise connectivity events. Graph theory was then used in these data to examine and illustrate the patterns of connectivity across the range of species' propagule durations, spanning from 1 to 180 days. For each duration, a distinct graph was constructed, with coastal sites representing nodes and the edges weighted by the logarithmic transformation of the pairwise connectivity probabilities (Abecasis et al. 2023). These graphs were used to calculate and map the three centrality metrics: betweenness centrality, out-strength centrality, and harmonic centrality.

Results

Propagule duration dataset

Empirical propagule duration periods varied significantly across species and groups, ranging from a few days to several months, with 99% of observations falling under 165 days (Figure 1, see also Assis et al. 2021 and reference therein). Specifically, Ascidiacea, Hydrozoa, and sponges exhibited the shortest average durations, followed by Polychaeta, seagrasses, corals, and Bryozoa, then macroalgae, Mollusca, and Echinodermata, and finally, mangroves, fish, and Crustacea with the longest average durations (Figures 2-3). Notably, there was high variability in propagule duration within groups as well (Figure 2; Table 1), as exemplified by macroalgae, where spore duration is short but broken thalli can float for extended periods, enabling long-distance dispersal (Bernardes Batista et al. 2018).

Oceanographic connectivity estimates and graph theory

Increasing propagule duration periods led to an increase in the number of connected pairs of sites (from 5.6 to 25.8 million pairs of sites; Figure 4) and average connectivity distances (from 24.71 ± 32.00 to 431.43 ± 356.17 km; Figure 4), although the distribution of these distances remained positively skewed (Figure 5). Such skewed patterns translated into a logarithmic increase in the number of connectivity events between sites with increasing propagule durations, reaching a plateau at around day 20 (Figure 4). For example, between days 1 and 10, the number of connectivity events increased by 305%, while between days 30 and 40 connectivity events increased only by 0.9%. Concurrently, out-degree and harmonic centrality also increased with propagule duration, while betweenness centrality had its peak at day 5 (Figure 4).

Species with shorter propagule durations (e.g., 5 days) exhibited connections strictly along coastlines (Figure 6). As propagule duration increased, so did the extent and complexity of the connectivity networks. At 10 days, connections emerged across the Gibraltar Strait, Skagerrak, Northern Aegean Sea, Marmara Sea and between Britain and Ireland (Figure 7). With a 20-day duration, the network expanded, linking continental coastlines to the Balearic Islands, Britain, Corsica, Sardinia, Sicily and Crete (Figure 8). A 40-day duration facilitated widespread connectivity across the Mediterranean Sea, and from the western Morocco coast to the Canary Islands, a trend strengthening the network that continued until 60-day duration (Figures 9-10). By 120 days, even distant locations like the Azores, Iceland, and Svalbard became connected to continental coastlines (Figure 11). Finally, at 180 days, the network reached its most consolidated state, with robust connections established across vast distances (Figure 12).

Betweenness centrality showed no clear pattern at 5 days (Figure 6), and decreased in isolated islands (e.g., Svalbard, Iceland, Corsica, Sardinia, and Gotland) as propagule duration increased

(Figures 7-9). With durations of 60, 120, and 180 days, the role of betweenness centrality further reduced in the northeastern Mediterranean Sea (Figures 10-12).

For species with low propagule durations (e.g. 5 and 10 days), hotspots of out-strength centrality concentrated in northern regions like Svalbard, Norway, and Scotland, as well as in the southern Iberian Peninsula and Marmara Sea (Figures 6-7). Increasing propagule duration (i.e. from 20 to 180 days) expanded out-strength centrality to include areas like Crete, Cyprus, the northeastern Mediterranean, and the southern Black Sea as propagule duration increased (Figures 8-12).

The relative role of harmonic centrality with increased propagule duration changed from northern European regions and the southern Iberian Peninsula towards the Alboran Sea, the Western Mediterranean, and areas around western Norway, Skagerrak, and the eastern Britain (Figures 6-12). These consistently well-connected areas, acting as hubs for a group of species with varying propagule durations, are likely highly more resilient and adaptable. Conservation efforts should therefore prioritize these hubs, as they have the potential to maintain the connectivity and integrity of the network, and therefore safeguard a wide range of marine species.

Discussion

The modelling approach employed has three main limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the ~5 km resolution of the oceanographic connectivity estimates (Assis et al. 2024), while previously validated at various scales (Assis et al. 2022; Buonomo et al. 2017; Gouvêa et al. 2023), may not fully capture fine-scale current dynamics and therefore preclude site scale connectivity patterns. Second, these estimates focus on surface currents, potentially overlooking the influence of deeper currents on dispersal pathways (Zhu and Liang 2020). Third, the model doesn't account for larval behaviour, or juvenile and adult movements, which could impact localized connectivity patterns (Abecasis et al. 2009; Shanks 2009; Vandeperre et al. 2014).

Using ocean currents alone to predict biological connectivity has several significant limitations. It may overestimate dispersal because eggs and larvae may die due to insufficient energy reserves and/or unsuitable environmental conditions. It may also overestimate dispersal because most, if not all, larvae have vertical and/or horizontal movement behaviours that may restrict their dispersal and aid their retention in suitable parental areas. However, it may also underestimate dispersal due to the mobility of juvenile and adult life-stages. The abundance of propagules, as well as the larval types (e.g. lecithotrophic vs. planktotrophic larvae) is also important, because the more eggs and larvae that are produced, with long long-larval nutrition strategy, then the further that some individuals will be dispersed. At local scales tidal currents rotate and reverse so a species can be dispersed against the prevailing ocean current. This suite of conditions mean that ocean currents may have limited effect on the actual distribution of most species, while changing environmental factors, such as temperature, pH, salinity, oxygen, ultraviolet radiation, and turbidity, will affect the survival of larvae and alter their behaviour (Bashevkin et al. 2021). Nevertheless, considering that marine species are adjusting their distributions in response to ocean warming, it may be that ocean currents are important in the pace of such changes in biodiversity.

The present analysis indicates that areas like western Norway, the Skagerrak, and the Iberian Peninsula consistently emerge as sources and/or corridors for marine connectivity. These findings will be used to assess and optimize the proposed network of MPAs to ensure long-term conservation of regional biodiversity pools. Thus, MPA Europe will consider the known and modelled distributions of species in designing an optimal network of MPA, and then see how oceanographic currents may connect areas within this network.

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Table 1. Summary of propagule duration data per group. Number of species, records, propagule duration (PD) period in days (average \pm SD), range of propagule duration and 95th percentile of propagule duration distribution per group.

Group	Species	Records	PD (day)	PD range	PD 0.95 quantile
Asciacea	11	91	1.18 \pm 0.40	1 - 2	2.00
Bryozoa	12	94	15.42 \pm 38.86	1 - 133	82.95
Corals	44	274	9.82 \pm 10.70	1 - 55	30.85
Crustacea	33	143	42.67 \pm 52.71	1 - 266	126.00
Echinodermata	237	1033	30.37 \pm 31.48	2 - 167	106.20
Fish	164	42727	43.93 \pm 37.63	1 - 210	125.95
Hydrozoa	7	30	3.00 \pm 3.42	1 - 8	8.00
Macroalgae	34	200	20.15 \pm 37.97	1 - 150	111.00
Mangroves	24	100	59.58 \pm 54.65	8 - 208	175.80
Mollusca	137	495	22.29 \pm 16.22	1 - 77	55.60
Polychaeta	32	75	11.97 \pm 10.55	1 - 34	34.00
Seagrasses	16	376	12.00 \pm 17.36	2 - 74	35.75
Sponges	13	51	3.69 \pm 3.04	1 - 8	8.00

*Figure 1. Frequency of empirical records of propagule duration periods. Vertical dashed line depicts the 99th percentile of the propagule duration periods of 165 days, while the * depicts the 95th percentile of the propagule durations of 180 days (see also Figure 3).*

Figure 2. Distribution of propagule duration periods per group. Vertical lines depict the mean (red) and the extreme 95th percentile (dashed) of propagule duration across observations.

Figure 3. Dendrogram clustering groups based on average propagule duration periods.

Figure 4. Metrics of oceanographic connectivity across propagule durations. Pairs of connected sites (panel a), connectivity events between sites (panel b), average connectivity distance between sites (panel c), average betweenness centrality (panel d), out-strength centrality (panel e), and harmonic centrality as a function of propagule duration (panel f).

Figure 5. Frequency of the distances of connectivity events for 5 days (panel a), 10 days (panel b), 30 days (panel c), 60 days (panel d), 120 days (panel e) and 180 days (panel f) of propagule duration. Vertical dashed lines depict the 99th percentile of connectivity distances.

*Figure 6. Connectivity and centrality for species with 5-day propagule duration. Connected pairs of sites (top- left), betweenness centrality (top-right), out-strength centrality (bottom-left), and harmonic centrality (bottom-right). Colors indicate the relative level of centrality within the network, with **blue** representing low, **yellow** representing moderate, and **red** representing high centrality.*

Figure 7. Connectivity and centrality for species with 10-day propagule duration. Connected pairs of sites (top- left), betweenness centrality (top-right), out-strength centrality (bottom-left), and harmonic centrality (bottom-right). Colors indicate the relative level of centrality within the network, with **blue** representing low, **yellow** representing moderate, and **red** representing high centrality.

Figure 8. Connectivity and centrality for species with 20-day propagule duration. Connected pairs of sites (top- left), betweenness centrality (top-right), out-strength centrality (bottom-left), and harmonic centrality (bottom-right). Colors indicate the relative level of centrality within the network, with *blue* representing low, *yellow* representing moderate, and *red* representing high centrality.

*Figure 9. Connectivity and centrality for species with 40-day propagule duration. Connected pairs of sites (top- left), betweenness centrality (top-right), out-strength centrality (bottom-left), and harmonic centrality (bottom-right). Colors indicate the relative level of centrality within the network, with **blue** representing low, **yellow** representing moderate, and **red** representing high centrality.*

*Figure 10. Connectivity and centrality for species with 60-day propagule duration. Connected pairs of sites (top- left), betweenness centrality (top-right), out-strength centrality (bottom-left), and harmonic centrality (bottom-right). Colors indicate the relative level of centrality within the network, with **blue** representing low, **yellow** representing moderate, and **red** representing high centrality.*

*Figure 11. Connectivity and centrality for species with 120-day propagule duration. Connected pairs of sites (top- left), betweenness centrality (top-right), out-strength centrality (bottom-left), and harmonic centrality (bottom-right). Colors indicate the relative level of centrality within the network, with **blue** representing low, **yellow** representing moderate, and **red** representing high centrality.*

*Figure 12. Connectivity and centrality for species with 180-day propagule duration. Connected pairs of sites (top- left), betweenness centrality (top-right), out-strength centrality (bottom-left), and harmonic centrality (bottom-right). Colors indicate the relative level of centrality within the network, with **blue** representing low, **yellow** representing moderate, and **red** representing high centrality.*

2024